

Protocol

Heated humidified high-flow oxygen therapy in patients admitted to intensive or intermediate care units

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A DASAIM clinical practice guideline

Background: The use of heated humidified high-flow oxygen therapy (HHHF) is widespread in intensive care units (ICUs).¹ HHHF is an open oxygen delivery system, which supplies heated humidified oxygen at high flow rates and at various concentrations. It is usually applied through specific high-flow nasal cannulas although oxygen masks and tracheostomy interfaces adapted to HHHF also exist.² A treatment with humidified heated oxygen supplementation in an open system is typically considered HHHF if the flow level exceeds 15 L/min.³

Due to the possibility to deliver flow levels of up to 60 L/min,³ HHHF is able to match the peak inspiratory flow rates of most patients, thus delivering a maximal FiO₂ of up to 1.00.^{4,5} A feature, which is not possible through conventional open oxygen supplementation systems like nasal cannulas, simple face masks, or venturi masks, and which may explain the widespread use of HHHF in hypoxaemic respiratory failure.³ Additionally, at high flow rates, a minor continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) effect may be present,^{6,7} and the heated humidification may improve ciliary motion and aid the clearing of bronchial secretions.⁸ HHHF also washes out carbon dioxide from the anatomical dead space.⁸ These physiological effects are theoretically relevant in the treatment of acute hypercapnic respiratory failure, i.e. in exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) as well.⁸⁻¹⁰

A recent European guideline have issued recommendations for HHHF in perioperative patients,¹¹ and a national Danish guideline exists for patients admitted to general wards.¹² However, despite the widespread use of HHHF in intensive care and intermediate care settings, and the existence of several randomised controlled trials and systematic reviews on HHHF in various ICU populations,^{13,14} no clinical practice guideline on HHHF in the intensive or intermediate care settings exists.

We represent a working group, which has been formed under the Danish Society of Anaesthesiology and Intensive Care Medicine (DASAIM) with representation from the Danish Society of Respiratory Medicine (DLS), to conduct a national Danish clinical practice guideline on HHHF use in patients admitted to ICUs or intermediate care units.

Objectives: We aim to produce a Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluations (GRADE)-based¹⁵ national Danish clinical practice guideline on the use of HHHF in adult patients admitted

to ICUs or intermediate care units. The overall clinical question that will be assessed is: Can HHHF improve the clinical outcomes of adult patients treated for respiratory failure in intensive or intermediate care units?

Methods

Protocol

The full protocol was finalised and accepted by all panel members prior to beginning the guideline process. The final protocol is uploaded to zenodo.org: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4106404>.

Populations, interventions, comparators, outcomes (PICO)

We will ask the following 10 specific PICO questions:

1. Should HHHF vs. conventional oxygen treatment in open systems (with or without intermittent mask CPAP) be used for hypoxaemic respiratory failure in adult patients admitted to intensive or intermediate care units?
2. Should HHHF vs. non-invasive ventilation (NIV) or mask CPAP be used for hypoxaemic respiratory failure in adult patients admitted to intensive or intermediate care units?
3. Should HHHF vs. conventional oxygen treatment in open systems (with or without intermittent mask CPAP) be used for hypercapnic respiratory failure in adult patients admitted to intensive or intermediate care units?
4. Should HHHF vs. NIV or mask CPAP be used for hypercapnic respiratory failure in adult patients admitted to intensive or intermediate care units?
5. Should HHHF vs. conventional oxygen treatment in open systems (with or without intermittent mask CPAP) be used for prophylactic respiratory support in high re-intubation risk adult patients post-extubation in the ICU?
6. Should HHHF vs. NIV or mask CPAP be used for prophylactic respiratory support in high re-intubation risk adult patients post-extubation in the ICU?
7. Should HHHF vs. conventional oxygen treatment in open systems (with or without intermittent mask CPAP) be used in adult patients with new respiratory failure in the ICU post-extubation?
8. Should HHHF vs. NIV or mask CPAP be used in adult patients with new respiratory failure in the ICU post-extubation?

9. Should HHHF be used with a higher flow and lower oxygen concentration (high-flow/low-O₂) versus a lower flow and higher oxygen concentration (low-flow/high-O₂) strategy in adult patients with hypoxaemic respiratory failure admitted to intensive or intermediate care units?
10. Should HHHF be used with a higher flow and lower oxygen concentration strategy versus a lower flow and higher oxygen concentration strategy in adult patients with hypercapnic respiratory failure admitted to intensive or intermediate care units?

Questions 1 to 4 will additionally be asked for the following 7 subpopulations:

- a. In the subpopulation with pneumonia (bacterial, viral, fungal, or parasitic)?
- b. In the subpopulation with epidemic viral pneumonia (e.g. influenza or coronavirus disease 2019)?
- c. In the subpopulation with cardiopulmonary oedema?
- d. In the subpopulation of immunocompromised patients?
- e. In the subpopulation with exacerbation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)?
- f. In the subpopulation with exacerbation of asthma?
- g. In the subpopulation with interstitial pulmonary fibrosis?

HHHF will be defined as any open system delivering oxygen mixtures that are heated and humidified to near-physiological levels with flow rates > 15 L/min. Open systems will be defined as any oxygen supplementation system, which is not invasive mechanical ventilation, NIV or CPAP using a tight fitting positive pressure mask.

Hypoxaemic (or hypoxic) respiratory failure will be as described by study authors, and will additionally include studies in patients with typical hypoxaemic conditions (e.g. acute respiratory distress syndrome, interstitial pneumonia, cardiopulmonary oedema, influenza pneumonia and COVID-19), unless these specifically target hypercapnic patients. Similarly will hypercapnic respiratory failure be as described by study authors. COPD in exacerbation will count as hypercapnic respiratory failure.

Intensive and intermediate care units will be defined as high-dependency facilities admitting acutely ill patients with higher needs of medical care than what is supplied in general wards, these facilities includes (but are not limited to): ICUs, intermediate care units, emergency departments, coronary care units, step-up units, perioperative care units, and post-anaesthesia care units.

Adults will be defined as ≥ 15 years of age.

Patients at high re-intubation risk will be defined as any fragile patient population specifically selected by study authors including (but not limited to) patients with: old age, high prognostic mortality score (e.g. acute physiology and chronic health evaluation (APACHE), sequential organ failure assessment (SOFA), or simplified acute physiology score (SAPS)), failure of consecutive weaning or extubation trials, chronic cardiac failure, hypercapnia at the time of extubation, and COPD or other chronic respiratory disorders. New respiratory failure will be as described by study authors.

High-flow/low-O₂ and low-flow/high-O₂ strategies will be as described by the authors; any study evaluating HHHF strategies of separate flows and oxygen concentrations with identical oxygenation target levels between groups will be included.

Immunocompromised patients will be defined as patients with any cancer or haematological malignancy, patients with any solid organ or stem-cell transplant conducted, patients positive for humane immune-deficiency virus (HIV), patients with any other hereditary or acquired specific immunocompromising condition defined as such by study authors, or patients receiving any immune-suppressive therapy including but not limited to chemotherapy, corticosteroids, calcineurin inhibitors, inosine monophosphate inhibitors, or immune response modulating monoclonal antibodies.

All PICO questions will be investigating the prioritised outcomes of 1. Long-term all-cause mortality (death at longest follow-up) (rating: 9); 2. Short-term all-cause mortality (death at 0-90 days, including in-ICU and in-hospital mortalities) (rating: 9); 3. Serious adverse events (exploratorily defined according to the International Conference on Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Registration of Pharmaceuticals for Human Use Good Clinical Practice (ICH GCP) guidelines¹⁶ as any untoward medical occurrence that results in death, is life-threatening, requires hospitalisation or prolongation of existing hospitalization, results in persistent or significant disability/incapacity, or is a congenital anomaly/birth defect) (rating: 7); 4. Quality of life (as defined in the included trials) (rating: 6); 5. Use of intubation and invasive mechanical ventilation (rating: 6); 6. Days alive without mechanical ventilation (rating 6); 7. ICU length of stay (only for studies in ICU patients) (rating: 6); and 8. Hospital length of stay (rating: 6). According to GRADE methodology¹⁷ all outcomes have been prioritised and rated from 9 to 1 separately by all guideline participants as well as by one relevant ICU patient. The prioritised list is constructed by the median of these ratings (as stated in parentheses). Ratings of 7-9 are defined as ‘critical outcomes’ and include the mortality outcomes and the SAE-outcome, remaining outcomes are defined as ‘important, but not critical’.¹⁷ The ICU patient’s ratings overall corresponded well with the ratings from the guideline participants. The complete overview of the PICO questions is shown in *Table 1*.

Literature search

We will systematically search PubMed, Embase, and Cochrane Library using the search strategies specified below. Duplicates will be removed and all search results will be screened by at least two guideline group

members using Rayyan QCRI.¹⁸ We will include all parallel-group randomised clinical trials (RCTs) (individually and cluster-randomised) and systematic reviews and meta-analyses of such, which evaluates HHHF as defined above in comparison with any of the specified comparators in adult human subjects admitted to ICU or intermediate care settings. Cross-over trials, quasi-randomised trials, and before-and-after trials will be included if data from parallel-group RCTs are insufficient to make conclusions. Non-interventional observational studies, narrative reviews, case-series and case reports will be excluded, unless evidence from all other publication types is insufficient, in which case they will be evaluated to possibly derive an expert opinion. A flow-chart of included and excluded studies in the screening phases and of the finally included papers (as separated according to study type) will be presented.

Grading the evidence

All steps in the rating and grading of the evidence will be conducted using GRADEpro Guideline Development Tool, McMaster University, 2015 (developed by Evidence Prime, Inc.).

Quality of the evidence for each outcome will be assessed using the GRADE assessment criteria, ranging from high to very low. Evidence from RCTs starts as high-quality evidence and evidence from observational studies starts as low-quality evidence. The overall quality of evidence for each PICO question will be established as the lowest quality obtained among the critical outcomes.¹⁹ We will use GRADE evidence profiles (EDs) for these steps, and create GRADE summary of findings (SoF) tables to be presented in the final guideline publication.¹⁹

We will decide on the direction (for/against) and grade strength (strong/weak) based on four prioritised factors: 1) balance between desirable and undesirable outcomes (estimated effects), with consideration of values and preferences (estimated typical), 2) Confidence in the magnitude of estimates of effect of the interventions on important outcomes (overall quality of evidence for outcomes), 3) Confidence in values and preferences and variability, and 4) resource use.²⁰

Dissemination and publication

The drafted guideline will be sent for approval in the national Danish ICU guideline group at ICU symposium Hindsgavl, and after approval here, it will be forwarded to the committee for ICU treatment (UFIM) under DASAIM for final approval. The approved guideline will be sought published in a relevant peer reviewed journal. We will apply for endorsement of the approved and published guideline by the Scandinavian Society of Anaesthesiology and Intensive Care Medicine (SSAI).²¹

Schedule

Primo 2020: writing and approval of the guideline protocol. Ultimo 2020: literature search, screening, bias assessments and compiling outcome effects. 2021: grading the evidence and decision of recommendations,

writing of primary guideline draft. Ultimo 2021: Submission of primary guideline draft to participants in the national guideline meeting 2022. January 2022: Approval at national guideline meeting, or revision of the guideline draft according to meeting comments, submission to UFIM under DASAIM. Primo 2022: submission to peer reviewed journal. Summer/autumn 2022: application for endorsement by SSAI.

Participants

The guideline group consists of:

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Literature search strategies

Pubmed

Search (((("high flow"[Text Word] OR highflow[Text Word] OR "high-flow"[Text Word])) AND ("Oxygen Inhalation Therapy"[Mesh:NoExp] OR oxygen*[Text Word] OR "Oxygen"[Mesh:NoExp] OR O2[Text Word] OR nasal[Text Word] OR cannula*[Text Word] OR canulla*[Text Word] OR cannula*[Text Word] OR canula*[Text Word] OR catheter*[Text Word] OR prong*[Text Word] OR nose[Text Word] OR nostril*[Text Word] OR tube[Text Word] OR tubes[Text Word] OR mask[Text Word] OR masks[Text Word] OR "Tracheostomy"[Mesh] OR Tracheostom*[Text Word] OR Tracheotom*[Text Word] OR tracheal*[Text Word]))) OR (HFNC[Title/Abstract] OR HFNO[Title/Abstract] OR HHHF[Title/Abstract]))

Embase

No.	Query
#9	#7 NOT #8
#8	'conference abstract'/it
#7	#5 OR #6
#6	hfnc:ti,ab,kw OR hfno:ti,ab,kw OR hhhf:ti,ab,kw
#5	#3 AND #4
#4	'high flow':ti,ab,kw OR highflow:ti,ab,kw OR 'high-flow':ti,ab,kw
#3	#1 OR #2
#2	oxygen*:ti,ab,kw OR o2:ti,ab,kw OR nasal:ti,ab,kw OR cannulla*:ti,ab,kw OR canulla*:ti,ab,kw OR cannula*:ti,ab,kw OR canula*:ti,ab,kw OR catheter*:ti,ab,kw OR prong*:ti,ab,kw OR nose:ti,ab,kw OR nostril*:ti,ab,kw OR tube*:ti,ab,kw OR mask*:ti,ab,kw OR tracheostom*:ti,ab,kw OR tracheotom*:ti,ab,kw OR tracheal*:ti,ab,kw
#1	'oxygen therapy'/de OR 'oxygen'/exp OR 'tracheostomy'/exp OR 'nasal cannula'/exp

Cochrane Library

ID	Search
#1	[mh oxygen]
#2	MeSH descriptor: [Oxygen Inhalation Therapy] this term only
#3	[mh Tracheostomy]
#4	(oxygen* OR O2 OR nasal OR cannulla* OR canulla* OR canula* OR cannula* OR catheter* OR prong* OR nose OR nostril* OR tube* OR mask* OR Tracheostom* OR Tracheotom* OR tracheal*)
#5	#1 OR #3 OR #4

#6	"high flow" OR highflow OR "high-flow"
#7	#5 AND #6
#8	(HFNC OR HFNO OR HHHF):ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#9	#8 OR #7

Table 1 Populations, interventions, comparators, outcomes (PICO)

Clinical question	PICO questions			
	Populations ^a	Interventions	Comparators	Outcomes
Can HHHF improve the clinical outcomes of patients treated for respiratory failure in intensive or intermediate care units?	<p>1. Adult patients with hypoxaemic respiratory failure</p> <p>Subpopulations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Pneumonia b. Epidemic viral pneumonia c. Cardiopulmonary oedema d. Immunocompromisation e. Exacerbation of COPD f. Exacerbation of asthma g. Interstitial pulmonary fibrosis <p>2. Adult patients with hypercapnic respiratory failure</p> <p>Subpopulations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Pneumonia b. Epidemic viral pneumonia c. Cardiopulmonary oedema d. Immunocompromisation e. Exacerbation of COPD f. Exacerbation of asthma g. Interstitial pulmonary fibrosis <p>3. High re-intubation risk adult patients post-extubation in the ICU (prophylactic)</p> <p>4. Adult patients with new respiratory failure in the ICU post-extubation</p>	<p>1. HHHF^b</p> <p>2. HHHF^b with a higher flow and lower oxygen concentration strategy^c</p>	<p>1. Conventional oxygen treatment in open systems (with or without intermittent mask CPAP)</p> <p>2. NIV or mask CPAP</p> <p>3. HHHF^b with a lower flow and higher oxygen concentration strategy^c</p>	<p>1. Long-term all-cause mortality (death at longest follow-up)^d</p> <p>2. Short-term all-cause mortality (death at 0-90 days, including in-ICU and in-hospital mortalities)^d</p> <p>3. Serious adverse events (as according to ICH GCP¹⁶)^d</p> <p>4. Quality of life (as defined in the included trials)</p> <p>5. Use of intubation and invasive mechanical ventilation</p> <p>6. Days alive without mechanical ventilation</p> <p>7. ICU length of stay^e</p> <p>8. Hospital length of stay</p>

HHHF: heated humidified high-flow oxygen therapy, COPD: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; ICU: Intensive care unit; CPAP: continuous positive airway pressure, NIV: non-invasive ventilation, ICH-GCP: International Conference on Harmonisation Good Clinical Practice. a. All populations include patients admitted to intensive or intermediate care units only. b. HHHF is defined as heated humidified oxygen therapy in open systems at flow > 15 L/min. c. Not investigated for populations 3 and 4 or for subpopulations, and only compared with intervention 2 and comparator 3, respectively. d. Prospectively defined critical outcomes. e. Only for studies conducted in ICU patients